

colloquium-journal

ISSN 2520-6990

Międzynarodowe czasopismo naukowe

**Medical sciences
Economic sciences
Historical sciences
Biological sciences
Philological sciences
Pedagogical sciences**

№7(272) 2026

colloquium-journal

ISSN 2520-6990

ISSN 2520-2480

Colloquium-journal №7 (272), 2026

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(Warszawa, Polska)

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HISTORICAL SCIENCES

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THE PROGRESSIVE POLITICAL MOVEMENT IN THE CZECH LANDS 1897-1914.

Abstract.

The article examines the origins and development of the progressive movement in the Czech lands in the period from 1897 to 1914. The radical political movement was not a feature of the Czech people alone; similar processes took place among many peoples of Europe oppressed by empires at the end of the 19th century. The Czech radical movement included not only national and social parties, but also specific state-legal ones.

Key words: *Czech Republic, Austria-Hungary, political parties, progressive movement, youngczechs, radical political movement, World War I.*

Problem statement. At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, the Czech lands, which were part of Austria-Hungary, became the scene of significant socio-political changes. One of the political forces that influenced these changes was the progressive movement. Progressives advocated the modernization of society, the protection of national rights, the democratization of the political system, and social reforms. However, despite their influence on the political life of that time, the activities of the progressive movement in the Czech lands remain insufficiently studied.

Purpose of the article. Research on the origins, development, and influence of the progressive movement on the political and social life of the Czech lands in the period from 1897 to 1914. An important aspect is the analysis of the political ideology of the progressives, their political activities, as well as their role in the formation of Czech national consciousness and the struggle for independence.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The progressive movement has been actively studied by Czech scholars. Among them, it is worth highlighting the works of Kučera M. [1], who is one of the co-authors of a powerful study of political parties and movements in the Czech lands, as well as J. Tomasz [2], who thoroughly investigated the origins of the progressive movement and the cooperation of progressives with other parties. Czech scholars have also studied the lives and activities of prominent representatives of this political movement. It is worth highlighting the study of R. Vašek [3] dedicated to A. Kalina. Unfortunately, a comprehensive study of political parties and movements in the Czech lands during the Austro-Hungarian monarchy has not yet been carried out.

Presentation of the main material of the study. Starting from the second half of the 80s of the 19th century. in the Czech lands, signs of industrial development increasingly appeared. In the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy in the 60s-70s of the 19th century. the national liberation struggle of the peoples that were part of it intensified. In many ways, this aggravation was intensified as a result of the economic crisis that began in April 1873 with a rapid fall in share prices on the Vi-

enna Stock Exchange. As a result of the crisis, the importance of agriculture increased, and accordingly the role of the peasantry as a social stratum, which began an active struggle for its rights. This was especially important in the conditions of the Czech people's life in the empire, in which they did not have full civil rights and social protection. This contributed to the emergence of Czech political radicalism [1, p.333].

The radical political movement was not a feature of the Czech people alone; similar processes took place among many of the peoples of Europe oppressed by empires at the end of the 19th century. The Czech radical movement included not only national and social parties, but also specific state-legal parties. The state-legal wing of the Czech political movement was finally formed at the end of the 19th century. The revolution of 1848-1849 had a powerful influence on this process. The main demand of the representatives of this movement was the full restoration of Czech statehood, and not only the recognition of equality as a component of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy. The herald of Czech radicalism was the Young Czechs party, founded in 1886 by the brothers Edward and Julius Gregrov. Among the party's supporters were both bourgeois and intelligentsia, as well as workers and peasants [1, p.334].

During this period, the structure of Czech political parties was formed, which in the future would stand at the origins of the First Czechoslovak Republic. Political parties in their essence fully corresponded to the era of the so-called "bourgeois" parties, widespread in other European countries. The basis of their ideologies was the principle of equality of citizens before the law, widespread thanks to the French Civil Code. Thus, the Great French Revolution became the impetus for the emergence of democracy in Cisleithania. The democratic ideas of the Czech politicians were in harmony with the tendencies in the political views of the Hungarian Germans. However, despite the democratization of political views, anti-Slavic sentiments were widespread among the German population of Hungary [2, p.23].

The development of the Czech national movement took place not only in the field of political and economic interests. There was a dynamic process of self-awareness and struggle for their rights of various social and professional groups and communities. Socialist ideas spread among the working class, the struggle of women for equal rights was manifested in numerous feminist organizations, and the social emancipation of merchants, who abandoned outdated forms of business and gradually transformed into the bourgeoisie, was also noticeable.

After the restoration of the Czech University in Prague in 1882, students became a politically active part of the Czech community. The seeds of political radicalism fell on the fertile soil of the student community in the mid-1880s. It was among the youth that there were many supporters of the Young Czechs. Czech youth, graduates of the Czech university, sought the opportunity to work in the prestigious civil service, but these positions were filled mainly by citizens of German nationality. There was a significant number of law graduates who could not find work in their specialty, the same situation was in ministries, chancelleries and other state institutions. Not to mention the diplomatic service. Only a few representatives of the Czech people were able to find work there. The situation was a little better in the army, but the successes of the Czech officer corps did not even come close to the career growth of the Austrian and Hungarian officers [4, p.341].

Gradually, the slogans that were proclaimed at the congresses of radical Czech students were formed into a full-fledged political program. From the environment of educated progressive Czech youth, a cadre of petty bourgeoisie and merchants was formed, which became the financial support of future progressive parties. The main slogan was the right of Czechs to be full citizens and to have equal rights and opportunities in Czech lands. Accordingly, slogans were raised about the restoration of Czech statehood within its historical borders. To achieve the dominant position of the Czech nation, according to the progressives, it was necessary, first of all, to carry out radical social reforms that would raise the standard of living of the population. The second important step should have been the proclamation of the autonomy of the Czech Republic. The borders of the autonomy should have been determined by the linguistic principle. That is, a regional autonomous region should have been established, the majority of whose population speaks Czech [5, p.21].

An inspiring example for the Czech progressive movement was the representatives of the Polish student radical movement, who in January 1890 gathered in Krakow for a rally dedicated to the idea of a united Poland, as well as the recognition of the rights of the "people and the proletariat". In March 1890, Czech students organized a demonstration in support of their leader K. Sokol, who had been expelled from Prague University for his views. In the first days of July, a delegation consisting of Czech politicians A. Raszyn, A. Hajn, and W. Klofach arrived in Krakow to take part in events marking the anniversary of the outstanding Polish poet Adam Mickiewicz. In Krakow, Czech politicians were impressed by the political program of the Galician

Ukrainian Radical Party of Ivan Franko. The programs of the Polish and Ukrainian radicals were taken as a basis for creating the political program of the Czech progressives. This program was published in the "Journal of Czech Students" from June 1890 to January 1891. Its main author, A. Hain, understood that for the success of the future progressive party, it should not be only student-based. Despite the existence of a political program, a full-fledged party had not yet been created. On February 6, 1891, a meeting was held at which it was decided that during the March elections, the Progressives, with the support of the Young Czechs, would join the National Party of Freethinkers as a separate faction. The faction was officially called the Progressive Party [1, p.334].

On April 15-19, 1891, a congress of Slavic progressive youth and students was held in Prague. The left wing of the Young Czech Party and the radically oriented workers were represented at the congress. It was headed by A. Vesely and V. Čížek. As a result of this congress, as well as congresses of social democrats in Brno (24-26.12.1887) and the Austrian Heinfeld (30.12.1888 - 1.01. 1889), radical workers' circles were formed from among the youth who worked in the metallurgical, mining, sewing, and printing industries. The following tendencies were characteristic of the circles: radical solution of the social question (as among the social democrats), a tendency to insurrectionary sentiments (as among the anarchists), national radicalism (as among the progressives). The followers of the third trend, the radically minded workers, formed the Workers' Political Club in the spring of 1890. During this period, the portrait of a progressive was formed. He was a citizen who was against the domination of a nation over a nation, a class over a class, and a person over another person [1, p.335].

In the Progressive Party, which continued to be part of the Young Czechs, two wings were formed. The first, led by A. Raszyn, advocated rapprochement with the state-law camp. The second, led by A. Hain, advocated cooperation with the labor movement. In the end, both wings agreed to cooperate with the Workers' Political Club, led by A. Veselý. Together they decided that the faction would in the future be the voice of its nation, which would defend its rights and demand the federalization of Austria-Hungary with the full independence of its subjects, which should be determined on the basis of the right of peoples to self-determination.

The progressives convened the second congress of Slavic progressive youth on June 5-7, 1892, which was attended by representatives of Poles, Ukrainians, Slovenes and Croats. The congress adopted a joint program, and the "Journal of Czech Students" was designated as the printed organ of all progressives of the empire [2, p.25].

Unfortunately, despite such positive trends, the progressive movement did not remain united for long. A group of individualists, led by F. Modracek, broke away from the Workers' Political Club of A. Veselý in protest against the unification with the Young Czechs. They began to call themselves independent socialists and began to approach the Social Democrats.

A bright page of the progressive movement was the participation of its representatives in protests for the introduction of universal suffrage. It was the progressives who became the core of the "Youth" organization, whose members were tried for organizing riots in Prague, which were accompanied by violence and pogroms. This was a political trial that took place in 1893-1894. [6, p.794].

As a result of the trial, 68 people received various terms of imprisonment. Among them were the leaders of the progressives: A. Rashin, A. Hain, A. Vesely, F. Modráček. In 1895 they were amnestied. From that time on, the progressive movement ceased to be united and split into several different branches[9].

The Progressive Socialist Party, founded in 1896, was the first to emerge from the ruins of the once unified progressive movement. On March 8, 1896, a part of the progressives officially left the Young Czechs, and on March 22, 1896, the establishment of the Progressive Socialist Party was announced. The party leaders A. Vesely, F. Modracek, and J. Skalák submitted a party program for publication in April 1896 under the title Principles of Progressive Socialists. The program had much in common with the theses of the Social Democrats. The Czech researcher of the progressive movement M. Kučera defines the political ideology of the party, based on its program, as liberal anarchism [8, p.93].

The program emphasized the importance of making quality education available to every citizen, the formation of a class of skilled workers, and support for the international socialist movement. The party sought to become part of the Social Democrats, but at the same time, it differed from them in some programmatic aspects. In particular, the progressive socialists rejected the ideas of the revolutionary formation of an independent Czech state [8, p.94]. The party had a small number of supporters, among them were burghers, peasants, and some supporters of anarchism joined its ranks. Understanding that with such a low popularity of the party, it had little chance of development, the leaders planned to merge with the Social Democrats in the future [7].

In political activity, things went badly for the party right away. In the summer, the authorities closed their printed organ, "Journal of Progressive Students," and party members were persecuted, as the Austrian authorities considered the party a haven for anarchists and radicals. The party's inability to publish its own newspaper in the long term led to the need to look for other opportunities. The solution was the initiative of F. Sokup and F. Tomaszko to start publishing an independent journal, "Academy." In December 1897, A. Vesely became the co-editor of the journal. When A. Vesely, the head of the Party of Progressive Socialists, became the editor of the social-democratic weekly "Zhar" in July 1897, it became clear that the party was ceasing to exist. Most of its members joined the ranks of the Social Democrats [1, p.338].

Another progressive party was the Czech Radical Progressive Party. At its origins stood A. Hein, who in April 1897 began publishing the weekly "Independence". In the introductory article of the first issue of the

weekly, A. Hein defined the main principles of the progressive movement. Among them: the restoration of the Czech state within its historical borders, democratic rights and freedoms for the Czech nation, equal social, cultural, and economic rights for the entire people, and the protection of the rights of workers and peasants from the tyranny of big capital and landowners. In fact, this article can be considered the proclaimed program of the party, the founding congress of which was held on April 4, 1897. It was this party that most consistently remained faithful to the principles of the progressive movement, which were formed in the first half of the 1890s [1, p.339].

The core of the party was impoverished intellectuals and radically minded workers. The majority of party members sympathized with the ideas of the Social Democrats. Two trends immediately formed within the party. And Hain and his supporters advocated rapprochement with the Social Democrats, and voiced more moderate slogans regarding the ways of restoring Czech statehood. His opponents, among whom A. Raszyn, K. Sokol, J. Třebický stood out, were against rapprochement with the Social Democrats, considering the slogans of the class struggle obsolete [2, p.44].

The party leader A. Hein was ready for compromises and expanded cooperation with other parties. There were ongoing disputes within the party about who was better to cooperate with, the Social Democrats or the National Socialists. Another problem was the issue of anti-Semitism. And Hein condemned anti-Semitic sentiments among some party members. In his opinion, the reason for this phenomenon was the long-term dominance of German and Jewish capital in the Czech lands. He advocated the Czech-Jewish assimilation movement, considering it a weapon against anti-Semitism. Among the important steps, Hein called the introduction of education among the population, as well as encouraging it to engage in entrepreneurial activity. These ideas were largely in line with the ideas of T.H. Masaryk and created the basis for negotiations on merging with the realists. However, the anti-Semitic wing of the party was too strong and the negotiations came to nothing [8, p.98].

Eventually, the left wing of the party left its membership. The leaders of the progressive socialists A. Hain and K. Sokol decided to remain faithful to the principles of the progressive movement under any circumstances. They managed to occupy influential positions in the youth movement, in particular in the Union of Czechoslovak Students, in which there was a struggle for influence between anarchists and realists. To participate in the 1907 elections, the progressive socialists united with other progressive parties into a single bloc. After the elections, the party leaders participated in the development of a bill on universal suffrage, which was the cornerstone of the ideology of progressivism. Eventually, in April 1908, the party merged with the Union of Radical Progressive Youth led by H. Čádek and the Czech State-Law (Constitutional) Progressive Party was created. [1, p.339].

After the elections of 1907, a new stage in the history of the progressive movement began. The previous period of 1890-1907 became the basis for the next, pre-

war stage of 1908-1914. The introduction of universal suffrage for men over the age of 24 in 1907 marked an important step in the process of democratization of public life in Cisleithania. Conditions were created for the participation of wider segments of the population in state governance. Therefore, changes in party programs for voter agitation became necessary. In addition, the electoral reform did not affect the solution of the Czech national question [4, p.358].

During the founding congress of the Czech State-Law Progressive Party on April 20, 1908, A. Hain noted that the true constitutional rights of the Czechs were possible for them only in their own state. He also voiced the main provisions of the political program of the newly created party: the struggle for their own statehood on the basis of Czech constitutional law; education in the Czech language in the Czech lands; defense of the right to use the Czech language in the army and in the civil service [8, p.104]. The Progressive Party of State and Law was founded in a turbulent time. The year 1908, the sixtieth anniversary of the reign of Emperor Franz Joseph I, brought an extraordinary deterioration of the domestic political situation in Bohemia and a serious international crisis that erupted in connection with the Austro-Hungarian annexation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and threatened to escalate into a military conflict of a pan-European scale. Anti-imperial and anti-German slogans were increasingly heard among the political sentiments of the Czechs.

Some citizens considered the preservation of the monarchy important for the expansion of Czech capital and the implementation of social reforms. However, the national contradictions between the Czechs and the Germans intensified, especially in the Czech lands. Czech and German politicians periodically tried to sit down at the negotiating table and find an understanding, but all attempts were unsuccessful [2, p.52].

German obstruction of the Czech regional elections paralyzed the country's local self-government for a long period and in July 1913 led to the dissolution of the Sejm and its replacement by an administrative commission consisting of civil servants. Thus, the regional autonomy of Bohemia was effectively eliminated. The activities of the progressives in these difficult conditions, in the pre-war years, focused on consolidating the ranks of their supporters, improving their financial situation and finding allies. Important events of this period were the elections to the Chamber of Deputies, which took place in the spring of 1911, and the general party congress in April 1912. [1, p.339].

The party represented primarily the interests of the bourgeoisie, had almost no workers in its ranks, but could boast a large number of representatives of the intelligentsia. It was aimed primarily at confronting Young Czech positivism, to which it opposed the alternative of a radical national party. At the same time, the party leaders repeatedly emphasized that national Czech interests should prevail over class interests. Czech researcher D. Tomasz, characterizing the party's activities, noted the following: "It had a detailed program, clearly defined goals and principles, but poor organization. In political practice, the party was distinguished by theoreticalism, and in gaining the support of

the electorate it turned out to be ineffective due to its idealism and fanaticism. Moreover, the party's ideologists did not realize the severity of a number of economic and socio-political problems or treated them conservatively [8, p.124].

As expected, the Progressive Party of the State Law suffered a defeat in the elections. The party was not prepared for the elections, did not mobilize its members, did not have money for agitation, and to top it all off, it was internally weakened by repressions by the imperial authorities. And so, 14,000 votes were cast for the Constitutional Progressives. Therefore, in the new lower house, the party was represented by only two deputies (instead of the previous five): the popular Antonin Kalina and the city councilor of Klatovsk, Václav Pruner (formerly a deputy of the regional parliament) [3, p.68].

In early July 1911, the Association of Independent Progressive Deputies from Bohemia and Moravia was created, headed by T.H. Masaryk and co-founded by A. Kalina. The cooperation of deputies of the State-Right Progressive Party, the Czech Progressive (Realist) and the Moravian People's Progressive Party in a joint association then reflected the general tendency of these three opposition parties towards rapprochement, which then intensified in the last pre-war years. It is worth noting that the subject of this rapprochement and joint progress was mainly the young generation of the aforementioned parties. The young realists, in particular, began to reject the hostility of the "old realists" to radicalism, thereby approaching the spirit of the State-Right Progressive Party.

Similarly, the "old realist" T.H. Masaryk revised some of his original views on evolution and revolution, as well as on Czech state law, which gradually ceased to be the object of criticism of the realist press. The position of the realists changed, who approached the position of the state-legal progressives, and not vice versa. At the same time, this rapprochement cannot be considered complete agreement. The relations between the leaders of the state-legal progressives and the realists, between A. Hein, V. Dick on the one hand and T.H. Masaryk, J. Gerben, J. Machar on the other, were quite tense [8, p.154].

In the last pre-war years, the State-Law Progressive Party also developed very lively contacts with the Moravian People's Progressive Party, the second most influential party in Moravia, which combined radical Young Czech ideology with realist-progressive elements and defended the right of the Czech people to self-determination [1, p.339].

The more international tension grew, the more the constitutional progressives spoke of a great European war as an opportunity to proclaim an independent Czech state. With the approval of the party chairman, its members – deputies A. Kalina and Dr. V. Stepanek established contact with the Russian consul in Prague Zhukovsky. The Constitutional Progressives offered Russia their assistance in the event of its military conflict with Austria-Hungary, but the consul rejected their offer and told A. Kalina that Russia did not count on a revolution in the Czech lands, which would be pointless given the Russian military plan, according to which the

Russian army did not intend to enter Czech territory [3, p.70].

This attitude of Zhukovsky towards the constitutional progressives was to some extent in contrast to his project of subversive actions in Bohemia after the outbreak of the war, which he carried out with the active assistance of the National Socialist Party. The consul's restraint towards the State-Law Progressive Party was probably based on its insignificant influence, small number of members and unstable financial situation. During the meetings, Zhukovsky did not deny the possibility of war, but did not count on the outbreak of war before 1915, which partly influenced the further progress of the party in view of this forecast. The party also tried to find support from representatives of Great Britain and France [8, p.153].

The First World War broke out in the middle of summer, during vacations, holidays and harvest. It shocked almost all contemporaries, even representatives of the party that had been waiting for it for many years and associated with it the decisive advance of the Czech national liberation struggle. It found most Czech politicians, including the Constitutional Progressives, on their country vacation. Due to the situation on the railways caused by the movement of troops, they only reached Prague many days later and began to consider their further actions in mutual contacts. At the same time, almost from day to day they found themselves face to face with the new conditions of war, which manifested themselves in the actual military-police dictatorship and unprecedented censorship. The Constitutional Progressives were among the first to start organizing conspiratorial discussion circles, as well as openly protesting against the anti-Czech and anti-Slavic policies of the military command and the growth of German chauvinism.

Conclusions. Thus, the progressive movement in the Czech lands in the period 1890-1914. went through a complex evolutionary process. From a small spark, the desire of student youth to have equal rights for all nations in their state, to a constitutional party that fights shoulder to shoulder with its people for independence in conditions of war and repression. Analyzing the activities of the most prominent representatives of the progressive movement, it is necessary to note their principledness and loyalty to the ideas of the progressive development of the Czech nation. Any concessions in order to conclude an alliance with other political parties for its leaders A. Hein, A. Kalina, F. Sokol were always accompanied by long intellectual discussions, because for them the choice between losing the electorate and loyalty to the ideas was always obvious. Such principledness of the progressives did not contribute to their great popularity. Another important aspect was the influence on the development of the progressive movement of representatives of other Slavic peoples, in particular Ukrainians. After all, it was the political program of the Radical Party, written by Ivan Franko, that inspired the progressives when creating

their first political program. The study of political parties and movements of this period is yet another proof that Ukraine is part of the family of European peoples.

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